

Conformation stereoselective adapted for some steroids derivatives (Minireview)

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Abstract

Stereochemistry is important to characterize the function of the compounds. For several decades, there has been interest in the study of the conformations in various steroid derivatives. The aim of this study was to review different stereochemistry conformation adopted by some steroid derivatives and their corresponding synthesis. The different conformations that steroids adopt mainly in both A and D rings depend on the substituted functional groups.

Keywords: Steroids, Stereochemistry, Conformation, Pregnenolone, Estrone.

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1. Introduction

Stereochemistry of steroids has been of great relevance in the area of chemistry; analyzing these data, the aim of this study was to conduct a bibliographic review as follows:

1.1 Pregnenolone derivatives

Studies carry out by Szendi shows the stereoselective reaction of a pregnenolone derivative (Figure 1), starting from compound

acid 17-[1-(5,6-dihydro-4H-pyran-2-yl)-1-hydroxyethyl]-13-methyl-2,3,4,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-tetradecahydro-1H-cyclopenta[a]phenanthren-3-yl ester (**1**) using *m*-chloroperoxybenzoic acid as catalyst to form 20R,23R-3,20,23,26-tetrahydroxy-27-norcholest-5-en-22-one-3-acetate (**2a**) with 32% of yield, mp: 186-189°C, and a smaller amount of its 23S enantiomer (**2b**) [1].

Figure 1. Synthesis of 20R,23R-3,20,23,26-tetrahydroxy-27-norcholest-5-en-22-one-3-acetate (**2a**) and their enantiomer (**2b**). Reagents and conditions: i: *m*-Cl-C₆H₄-CO₃H/ MeOH; ii: H₃O⁺, iii: *m*-Cl-C₆H₄-CO₃H/ MeOH/pyridine. The compounds **3a** and **3b** were formed as an intermediary.

However, also in the reaction from compound **1**, can be form either intermediates **3a** or **3b**.

Other study showed a bromination stereoselective of (20R)-3,20-dihydroxy-(3',4'-dihydro-2'H-pyran-yl)-5-preg-nane (**4**) under lower temperature using nitrogen, after 30 min, is obtained two intermediates compounds (**5a**) and (**5b**). Then, the

intermediates mixture in reaction was acidified using TDA/CHCl₃ overnight for open the ring in C-3. After the crude product was chromatographed in a column of silica gel, yielding **7a** (67%) and **7b** (35%). In addition, it is important to mention that compounds such as **6a** and **6b** are prepared from compound **4**, using *m*-

chloroperoxybenzoic acid and methanol/pyridine (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Synthesis of pregnenolone derivatives. Reagents and conditions: i = *m*-chloroperoxybenzoic acid and methanol/pyridine; ii = Br/MeOH/N₂; iii = TDA/CHCl₃.

There are other report [2] about of the stereoselective synthesis of pregnenolone acetate derivatives; for example the synthesis of 22,25-diazacholesterol isomers (**8a-d**) from pregnenolone acetate (**8**), *N,N*-dimethylethylenediamine, *p*-TsOH and toluene under reflux overnight followed by treatment with the NaBH₄/MeOH/THF system (Figure 3). It is important to mention that the original chemical

structure had modified in two positions, first the acetate group was reduced in a hydroxyl group in C-3, but the most important modification was over the D ring, the insertion of an amino group employing a primary amine.

The diastereomers (**8a-d**) were purified via flash column chromatography on silica gel using the ethyl acetate: petroleum ether:triethyl amine system.

Figure 3. Synthesis of 22,25-diazacholesterol isomers (**8a-d**) Reagents and conditions. i: N, N-dimethylethylenediamine, ρ -TsOH (ρ -toluenesulfonic acid), toluene, reflux; ii: NaBH_4 , $\text{CH}_3\text{OH}/\text{THF}$, pH 6; K_2CO_3 in $\text{CH}_3\text{OH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Other study [3] showed the synthesis of two epimers 20R and 20S 20-aminopregn-5-en-3 β -ol (**10** and **11**) from 5-pregnen-3 β -ol-20-one (**9**), $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4/\text{NaBH}_3\text{CN}$ and MeOH at room temperature for 48 h (Figure 4). This process involves a reduction in C-20 to the synthesis of

the stereoisomeric amines mixture, which were separated through chromatography on grade II alumina using the $\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2/\text{EtOH}$ system; yielding, 75% for 20R isomer an mp: 222-223 °C, and for 20S isomer a mp: 177-178°C.

Figure 4. Synthesis of (20R) and (20S)-20aminopregn-5-en-3 β ol (**10** and **11**). Reagents and conditions; i: $\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2\text{NH}_4$, NaBH_3CN , CH_3OH .

1.2 Estrone derivatives

A study [4] showed the synthesis of the stereoisomer of (13*S*,17*S*)-13-methyl-7,8,9,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-decahydro-6H-cyclopenta[*a*]phenanthren-3,6,17-triol (**13**), from (13*S*,17*S*)-13-methyl-6,17-dioxo-

7,8,9,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-decahydro-6H-cyclopenta[*a*]phenanthren-3-yl acetate (**12**) THF, and LiAlH₄, to reduction of ketone group in C-6 and C-17 (Figure 5); yielding 52% of product, mp 210-212°C.

Figure 5. Synthesis of (13*S*,17*S*)-13-methyl-7,8,9,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-decahydro-6H-cyclopenta[*a*]phenanthren-3,6,17-triol (**13**); Reagents and conditions; i: LiAlH₄, THF.

In addition, **13** reacted with allylmagnesium bromide in the presence of LiAlH₄ to form a mixture of 6 α and 6 β -isomers which were

separated via chromatography on silica gel to form 16 α -hydroxyestradiol and 16 β -hydroxyestradiol.

Figure 6. Synthesis of 6 α - and 6 β -estradiol. Reagents and conditions: allylmagnesium bromide, LiAlH₄, THF, -78 °C.

1.3 Hydrocortisone derivatives

There are a report [5] which indicate the synthesis of compound **23** (Figure 8) has the configuration R in C₂₂, is obtained from compound acetic acid 2-(3,11-bis-benzyloxy-10,13-dimethyl-hexadeca-hydro-cyclopenta[a]-phenanthren-17-yl)-2-oxoethyl ester (**17**). The addition of ethylmagnesium bromide and NaIO₄ to **17** produce the compound

1-(3,11-Bis-benzyloxy-10,13-dimethyl-hexadeca-hydro-cyclopenta[a]phenanthren-17-yl)-propan-1-one (**18**). Then, **18** reacted with N-bromoacetamide in acetone and to give 1-(3,11-Bis-benzyloxy-17-bromo-16-hydroxy-10,13-dimethyl-hexadeca-hydro-cyclopenta[a]phenanthren-17-yl)-propan-1-one (**19**).

Figure 7. Synthesis of a hydrocortisone derivative (**25**). Reagents and conditions: i: ethylmagnesium bromide, NaIO₄; ii: iii: N-bromoacetamide acetone; iii: Bu₃SnH, triethylborane, iv: 1,1,2-trimethylbut-3-ynyltetrahydrofuran ether, LiAlH₄; v: Hg(OTf)₂, AcOH, CH₃CN. rt; vi: *p*-toluenesulfonate, CHCl₃, rt.

Following, a debromination of **19** mediated by n-Bu₃SnH and triethylborane was carried out to form 1-(3,11-Bis-benzyloxy-16-hydroxy-10,13-dimethyl-hexadeca-hydro-cyclopenta[a]phenanthren-17-yl)-propan-1-one (**20**). After, the compound **21** was prepared via reaction of **20** with 1,1,2-trimethylbut-3-ynyltetrahydrofuran ether in the presence of LiAlH₄. Additionally, a spirocetal (**22**) was obtained by reaction of **21** with Hg(OTf)₂ in acetonitrile/acetic acid. Finally,

the epimerization of compound **22** in C₂₂ using pyridinium *p*-toluenesulfonate in CHCl₃ produce the compound **23** with a yield of 80% [6].

A similarly report [5] for the synthesis of compounds **25**, **26** and **27** from compound **24**, treated with NaIO₄ on silica support in anhydrous CH₂Cl₂ that gives the compound **25** (85% yield). The reduction of **25** was developed using NaBH₄/EtOH to produce the compound **26**. In

addition, **27** was prepared via epimerization of **26** with pyridinium *p*-toluensulfonate/ CHCl_3 (yield 86%) (Figure 9).

Figure 8. Synthesis of a spiroacetal (**27**). i: $\text{SiO}_2\text{-NaIO}_4$, CH_2Cl_2 , rt; ii: NaBH_4 , EtOH; iii: pyridinium *p*-toluensulfonate, CHCl_3 , rt, 86%.

1.4 Androgen derivatives

There are some studies which shown the preparation of some epoxy-steroid derivatives [7]. For example, the epimeric compounds **28a** and **28b** (Figure 10) which are obtained from epoxidation of 10,13-Dimethyl-3-oxo-2,3,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-tetradecahydro-1H-cyclo-penta[a]phenanthrene-17-carboxylic acid methyl ester (**28**) employing as reagents

NaOH , H_2O_2 and CH_3OH , followed by a treatment with pyridine and acetic anhydride.

On the other hand, a diastereomeric mixtures (**29a** and **29b**) was obtained from 17-Acetyl-10,13-dimethyl-1,2,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-tetradecahydro-cyclo-penta[a]phenanthren-3-one (**29**) using some reagents such as NaOH and H_2O_2 . In addition, **30a** and **30b** were prepared from **30** with same conditions compared with **29a** and **29b** [8].

Figure 9. Epoxidation of 4-en-3-oxo-steroids; i, H₂O₂ /NaOH/ CH₃OH; ii, Ac₂O/pyridine.

On the other hand, a report showed the synthesis of compound **31a** (Figure 11), which is obtained via Clemmensen reduction of androstenedione (**31**) using zinc and acetic acid as reagents that produces an isomeric mixture (**32a** and **32b**);

then, mixture was crystallized with n-hexane to give **32a**. Finally, the epoxy-steroid derivative (**33**) was obtained from **32a** using performic acid and methylene chloride [9].

Figure 10. Synthesis of epoxide-steroid derivative (33); Reagents and conditions: i: CH_3COOH , Zn; performic acid, CH_2Cl_2 .

Other study showed [10] the preparation of an androgen derivative (Figure 12) was prepared from 10,13-Dimethyl-1,2,3,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16-tetradecahydro-cyclopenta[a]phenan-

thren-17-one (34) in the presence of OsO_4 and pyridine followed by reaction with NaHSO_3 , diluted in EtOAc to form an isomeric mixture (35 and 36).

Figure 11. Reagents: (i) OsO_4 , pyridine; (ii) Aqueous NaHSO_3 .

On the other hand, a report showed the synthesis of some androstan-4-en-3,17-diones substituted with 6α and 6β -phenylaliphatics (38 and 39) from 37, hydrochloric acid and EtOH, to give two substituted isomer in 6α (37-66% yield) and 6β (7-15% yield). In addition, reverse phase

chromatography with a mobile phase of acetonitrile-water was used to separating the 6α and 6β isomers [11].

Figure 12. Synthesis of androstan-4-en-3,17-diones substituted (**38** and **39**). Reagents and conditions: (i) 1M HCl, EtOH, reverse phase chromatography/acetone-water.

On the other hand, two androstan derivatives (**42** and **43**) were prepared from 6α - and 6β -phenylalkylandrostan-4-ene-3,17-diones (**40** and **41**), 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyano-1,4-benzoquinone (DDQ) and dry benzene, heating at reflux for 10 h under an atmosphere of N_2 , the reaction mixture

is passed through an Al_2O_3 column and elution with EtOAc, followed by purification in column chromatography with silica gel (Hexane-EtOAc) and HPLC (acetonitrile- H_2O) only in one step, resulting an unsaturation in A ring, between C-1 and C-2 [12].

Figure 13. Synthesis of 6α and 6β -phenylalkylandrostan-1,4-diene. Reagents and conditions (i) DDQ, benzene, reflux.

On the other hand, a report showed the stereoselective synthesis of two ester-steroid derivative (**45a**, 4%; and **45b**, 96%) from tert-butyl(((10S,13S)-10,13-dimethyl-1,2,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15-tetradecahydrospiro[cyclo-

penta[a]phenanthrene-3,2'-[1,3]dithiolan]-17-yl)oxy)dimethylsilane (**44**), tert-butyl dimethylsilyl trifluoromethanesulfonate (TBSOTf), silylene ether, ethylaluminum dichloride (EtAlCl_2) in the presence of hexafluoroisopropane (HFIP) [13].

Figure 14. Synthesis of ester-steroid derivatives (**45a** and **45b**). Reagents and conditions. i = TBSOTf, sylene ether, EtAlCl₂, HFIP.

2. Conclusions

In this study, a review of the different conformations adopted for some steroid derivatives was performed. It is important to mention that these conformations, which depend on the different functional groups, involved in their chemical structure.

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